

Deliverable D2.2.a “Training datasets for Statistical Downscaling”

Summary

Two main references for this deliverable::

- *Doury et al., Regional climate model emulator based on deep learning: concept and first evaluation of a novel hybrid downscaling approach, Climate Dynamics, 2023.*
- *Doury, Somot & Gadat, On the suitability of a convolutional neural network based RCM-emulator for fine spatio-temporal precipitation, Climate Dynamics, 2024.*

The two Doury et al. studies rely on EURO-CORDEX simulations performed with the ALADIN63 regional climate model at 0.11° resolution. In the temperature study, the emulator is trained on daily near-surface temperature from ALADIN63 driven by CNRM-CM5, using historical and RCP8.5 data, and evaluated on an independent RCP4.5 simulation over a 64 × 64 grid-point domain centered on southern France. In the precipitation study, the same framework is extended to daily precipitation over a larger 128 × 128 Alpine-centered domain, and the dataset includes the full ALADIN63 EURO-CORDEX simulation matrix, with several GCM drivers and scenarios. In both cases, the emulator is trained in a perfect-model framework using coarsened large-scale predictors derived from the RCM itself, together with external forcings and temporal indicators, in order to isolate and learn the downscaling function embedded in the regional climate model.

The datasets can be retrieved from

<https://github.com/antoinedoury/RCM-Emulator>

CordexBench

In parallel, the TRACCS-PC10 WP2 team has been contributing to a new ML-benchmark introduced by the CORDEX ML-taskforce: **CordexBench**. The contributions of the team were on the general conception of the challenge and also on defining the datasets and the metrics for validation. The TRACCS-PC10 team has also participated in the comparison by submitting two methods: the *CNRM-UNET* (described in Deliverable D21a) and *ParamUnet* (Legasa et al. In prep)

CORDEX ML-Bench is a benchmark designed to evaluate the performance of machine learning-based climate downscaling models across different regions covering both the standard (perfect prognosis ESD) and emulation climate downscaling approaches. It defines standardized training and test experiments assessing various downscaling challenges along with the corresponding datasets from Regional Climate Models (RCMs) driven by different Global Climate Models (GCMs). Data is prepared for three regions (ALPS, New Zealand, South Africa) and is available on Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/17957264>

Dataset composition

16 Predictors (coarse-resolution ~200km, 16×16 grid):

Atmo vars at 850 hPa, 700 hPa, 500 hPa:

- u - zonal wind component
- v - meridional wind component
- q - specific humidity
- t - temperature
- z - geopotential height
- Static field: Orography

Predictands (high-resolution ~10km, 128×128 grid):

- Temperature (tasmax)
- Precipitation (pr)

Two benchmark challenges

Training Data

Includes predictors and predictands for two benchmark experiments:

- ESD Pseudo-Reality: Standard empirical statistical downscaling
- Emulator Hist+Future: Physical emulation approach

Test Data

Includes predictors for three time periods (historical, mid-century, end-century) with:

- Perfect predictors: Upscaled from RCM (as in training)
- Imperfect predictors: From driving GCM

Domain	Resolution	Target Variables	Target Grid Size	Predictor Variables	Predictor Grid Size	Static Fields
New Zealand (NZ)	0.11°	Tsmax, Pr	128 x 128	u, v, q, t, z at 850, 700, 500 hPa (15 variables)	16 x 16 (2°)	Orography (128 x 128; 0.11°)
Europe (ALPS)	0.11°	Tsmax, Pr	128 x 128	u, v, q, t, z at 850, 700, 500 hPa	16 x 16 (2°)	Orography
South Africa (SA)	0.10°	Tsmax, Pr	128 x 128	u, v, q, t, z at 850, 700, 500 hPa	16 x 16 (2°)	Orography